

LEVEL OF HIV/AIDS AWARENESS AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF TEACHERS IN LUTAYAN DISTRICT 1 LUTAYAN SULTAN KUDARAT

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Level of HIV/AIDS Awareness and Preventive Measures of Teachers in Lutayan District 1 Lutayan Sultan Kudarat

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Abstract

This research investigates on the level of knowledge and use of preventive measures among teachers in Lutayan District 1, Lutayan Sultan Kudarat, about the Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS). HIV diagnoses have increased in the Philippines in recent years. This research employed qualitative and quantitative research designs. It described the HIV/AIDS awareness of teachers in terms of knowledge and attitudes in Lutayan District 1 in Sultan Kudarat. In the Philippines, there were projected to be 77,000 HIV-positive individuals by UNAIDS in 2020. To combat HIV/AIDS, the Philippine government has put in place a number of measures and programs, such as expanding access to services for prevention, treatment, and testing. Reaching important communities and overcoming societal stigma are still difficult tasks, though. The HIV/AIDS epidemic has been a major problem for the Philippines, and educators are vital in helping pupils become more aware of the disease and encourage preventive measures. The purpose of the study is to evaluate the teachers' attitudes regarding the illness as well as their knowledge of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies and transmission. The results of this study will highlight areas that need improvement and offer insightful information about how well teachers are currently being educated on HIV/AIDS. A safer and healthier learning environment for children and the larger community can be established by raising instructors' awareness and implementing preventive measures.

Keywords: *HIV, AIDS, awareness, preventive measures*

Introduction

The field of education for HIV/AIDS prevention, testing, and care is a recently emerging profession. It will work alongside medicine and public health to support the rapidly evolving multi-sectoral, global, and national strategies and programs aimed at reversing the current trends of the HIV pandemic. An important obstacle in the field of education for HIV/AIDS prevention, testing, and care is in understanding, examining, and studying the potential connections between HIV/AIDS and literacy.

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) possesses distinct characteristics: it is minuscule, dormant, constantly changing, but highly vulnerable outside of the body and challenging to spread. The virus, although not highly contagious and easily preventable, is exceptionally lethal because to its ability to exploit the fundamental biological drive that ensures the survival of the human species. "AIDS is the terminal phase of a deadly contagious illness, which starts with an HIV infection and advances to cause significant and severe harm to the body's immune system" (Schenker, 2009). AIDS is a viral disease caused by the human Immunodeficiency virus (HIV) that is typically present in bodily fluids such as blood, semen, vaginal fluid, and breast milk of infected individuals. The virus can be transmitted between individuals, mostly through sexual intercourse and the sharing of unsterilized equipment such as blades, knives, and syringes that have been previously used by infected individuals. (Olaleye, 2009). Health professionals have characterized the occurrence and expansion of HIV/AIDS in the Philippines as being at a low and gradual pace (Tacio, 2005; Mateo et al., 2005; HAIN, 2003). Since 1984, the first case of HIV/AIDS was recorded with the demise of an individual from another country. As of March 2005, the occurrence of HIV/AIDS was just 0.01%, which amounts to 2,250 cases in a population of approximately 85 million. The figure is hardly a cause for concern to the general public, particularly when compared to the statistics of neighboring Asian countries or when compared to the more alarming statistics of tuberculosis (TB) and malaria. The Department of Health (DOH) reports that tuberculosis (TB) causes the death of 75 individuals in the Philippines daily. Additionally, data from the World Health Organization (WHO) reveals that in 2003 alone, there were 43,644 recorded cases of malaria in the country (WHO, 2005).

The low prevalence and gradual spread of HIV/AIDS in the Philippines have perplexed both local and international specialists, as the necessary prerequisites for an explosive crisis are available. The 2002 report from the Department of Health's National HIV/AIDS Sentinel Surveillance System (NHSSS) provided several possible explanations: (a) the network of sex workers is not as extensive as in countries with high HIV prevalence; (b) the rate of injecting drug use is low, although other types of drug use may be more common; (c) the number of clients seen by sex workers per night is lower compared to Thailand and Africa; (d) social hygiene clinics are available to regularly examine and treat infected establishment-based female sex workers; and (e) there have been early and accelerated multi-sectoral responses to combat the threat of HIV/AIDS. According to the report, the low prevalence rate suggests that the virus has not yet reached a threshold in the population where it may spread rapidly. It is assumed that the disease is mainly affecting vulnerable people.

Given the aforementioned circumstances and the imperative of providing primary education to ethnic minority groups in a culturally relevant and geographically accessible manner, the researcher aims to investigate the level of HIV/AIDS awareness among teachers and their implementation of prevention measures.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the level of awareness and preventive measures of teachers in Lutayan District I Sultan Kudarat. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of awareness of HIV/AIDS of Teachers in Lutayan District I, Sultan Kudarat?
2. What are their preventive measures implemented?
3. What is the relationship between the knowledge of the teachers of HIV/AIDS and the preventive measures?

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a mixed-method qualitative and quantitative research designs. It described the HIV/AIDS awareness of teachers in terms of knowledge and attitudes in Lutayan District 1 in Sultan Kudarat. Moreover, it also determined the preventive measures through information and health education of teachers in their teaching-learning process in the classroom. The result of this endeavor helped school heads and teachers find an effective and concrete intervention to improve the learning processes for better school performance at local, regional, and national.

Participants

The population of Elementary schools in Lutayan 1 District, Division of Sultan Kudarat were the participants of this study. There were 121 teachers from 8 selected elementary schools namely: Tamnag Central Elementary School (34), Manili Elementary School (16), Mamali Elementary School (19), D' Leal Elementary School (9), Antong Elementary School (9), Maindang Elementary School (11), Sampao Elementary School (16) and Mangandog Elementary School (7).

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents of the Study

<i>School</i>	<i>Total Population of Elementary School Teachers</i>
Tamnag Central Elementary School	34
Manili Elementary School	16
Mamali Elementary School	19
D'Leal Elementary School	9
Antong Elementary School	9
Maindang Elementary School	11
Sampao Elementary School	16
Mangandog Elementary School	7
Total	121

Instruments

A questionnaire was used to gather data. For the HIV/AIDS awareness in Lutayan District 1 teachers a 42-item test was administered it was adapted and modified (Fraim, 2012). To analyze the result, the percentage was used:

80 - 100	Very High
60 – 79	High
40 – 59	Moderately High
20 – 39	Low
0 – 19	Very low

For HIV/AIDS preventive measures for teachers, a 15-item test was used, and it was adopted and modified (Vasan, 2000) and Fraim, 2012). To analyze the result, it was rated as true or false.

Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and Key Informant Interview (KII) were also done using a guide question.

Procedure

The researcher prepared a letter asking permission from the school division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and Principals regarding the collection of data. Upon the approval of the request, the researcher coordinated with the principals of different schools in Lutayan District 1 to obtain teacher lists as a guide in identifying the respondents. After the identification of the respondents, the researcher gathered the teachers in a vacant room to explain the objective of the study. The teachers have assigned seats so they can be seated comfortably to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire being administered. The researcher personally distributed the questionnaire to the teacher-respondents. Immediately after the respondents were done answering, the researcher collected the questionnaire and prepared them for statistical treatment. Statistical Treatment To determine the level of HIV/AIDS awareness of teachers, the mean, frequency count, and percentage will be used. To determine the level of HIV/AIDS preventive measures of teachers, frequency count and mean were used. To determine if there is a significant relationship between HIV/AIDS awareness and preventive

measures of teachers, Pearson r was used. All hypotheses will be done at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents analyses, and interprets the data gathered in this study. The various results are presented in the succeeding tables.

HIV/AIDS Awareness of Teachers

Table 2A presented the percentage and correct responses to HIV/AIDS Knowledge. The researchers noted the very high level of awareness of AIDS as Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (99%); AIDS caused by a virus (95%), AIDS is not serious (95.8%); and it cannot be transmitted by the tears of an infected person (91.7%).

There was also a high percentage of knowledge on AIDS as a contagious disease (85%); AIDS not being able to distinguish between HIV positive and not positive person (74.2%). Low scores were noted on the following: only one specific symptom of AIDS (40%); a person infected with HIV does not usually show any symptoms of the disease (55.8%) and seafarers are at risk of HIV (66.7).

Based on the interview conducted, the reason why the result is very high is that they get knowledge from televisions, radio, media, books, and networking sites. Low scores on the other hand were obtained on not knowing that HIV/AIDS can be passed through birth.

Table 2A. *HIV/AIDS Awareness of Teachers in Terms of Knowledge*

<i>Knowledge</i>	<i>Correct Responses</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
1. AIDS stands for Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome	119	99	Very High
2. AIDS is not serious: it's a simple disease like the common cold	115	95.8	Very High
3. AIDS is caused by a virus.	114	95	Very High
4. HIV/AIDS cannot be transmitted by tears of an infected person.	110	91.7	Very High
5. AIDS is a contagious disease.	102	85	Very High
6. We can distinguish AIDS patients from others by their appearance.	89	74.2	High
7. Urine, X-ray, total blood count, and biochemistry are used to check the HIV in the blood.	89	74.2	High
8. Seafarers, like anyone else, are at risk of HIV infection because of peer pressure.	80	66.7	High
9. HIV cannot be transmitted through sweating.	73	60.8	High
10. There is an active treatment for AIDS.	72	60.7	High
11. There is no vaccine for AIDS.	68	56.7	Moderately High
12. A person infected with HIV does not usually show any symptoms of the disease.	67	55.8	Moderately High
13. HIV/AIDS cannot be transmitted by mucus or nasal fluids from an infected person.	66	55.0	Moderately High
14. There is only one specific symptom of AIDS.	48	40.0	Moderately High
15. AIDS is a hereditary disease.	23	19.2	Very Low

The result of the study was supported by Kailings (2008) that HIV is spread primarily by unprotected sex (including anal and oral sex), contaminated blood transfusions, hypodermic needles, and from mother-to-child pregnancy, delivery, or breastfeeding. Some bodily fluids, such as saliva and tears, do not transmit HIV. Methods of prevention include safe sex, needle exchange programs, treating those who are infected, and male circumcision. Disease in a baby can often be prevented by giving both the mother and child antiretroviral medication. There is no cure or vaccine; however, antiretroviral treatment can slow the course of the disease and may lead to a near-normal life expectancy. Treatment is recommended as soon as the diagnosis is made. Without treatment, the average survival time is 11 years. Beyrer (2012) posited that training of teachers on the new HIV/AIDS curriculum was positively associated with the development of their skills and the building of confidence. Training on HIV/AIDS education increases the skills of teachers, which makes them more capable of teaching about HIV/AIDS-related issues and overcoming the barriers, particularly talking to students about sexuality by using interactive teaching methods in the classroom setting. The interactive teaching method seems to be more effective in teaching about HIV/AIDS, and, on such methods, more emphasis was given during training. There is a clear difference between the intervention and the control district in using such a method by the teachers.

In the intervention district, at least one teacher used such methods in a significantly higher proportion of schools compared to the control schools, indicating the necessity of training the teachers. HIV/AIDS Awareness of Teachers on Mode of Transmission The 2B presented the percentage of correct responses on HIV/AIDS Awareness of Teachers in terms of the HIV Mode of Transmission. The researcher noted very high scores on "AIDS" can be transmitted by having vaginal sex with the infected person (100.0%); it can be transmitted by the sperm of an infected person (98.3%); it can be transmitted by receiving blood with an infected person (98.3%); it can be transmitted by touching an infected person such as hugging, holding, and shaking hands (95.8%); it can be transmitted by donating the organs and tissues of an infected person to the other person (95.8%); it can be transmitted by having anal sex with an infected person (95%); it can be transmitted by sharing injection needles or surgical operation devices of an infected person (93.3%); it can be transmitted by sharing toilets and swimming pools with infected persons (90%) yes if there were fluids in the toilet bowl or

the swimming pool will pass through the vagina of another person the virus will also be transmitted.

Table 2B. HIV/AIDS Awareness of Teachers on Mode of Transmission

	Modes of Transmission of HIV/AIDS	Correct Responses	Percentage	Remarks
1.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by having vaginal sex with an infected person.	121	100	Very High
2.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by the vaginal fluid of an infected person.	119	99.2	Very High
3.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by receiving blood from an infected person.	118	99.3	Very High
4.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by the sperm of an infected person.	118	98.3	Very High
5.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by donating the organs and tissues of an infected person to the other person.	115	95.8	Very High
6.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by touching an infected person such as hugging, holding, and shaking hands.	115	95.8	Very High
7.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by having anal sex with an infected person.	114	95	Very High
8.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by sharing injection needles or surgical operation devices of an infected person.	112	93.3	Very High
9.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by sharing toilets and swimming pools with infected persons.	108	90	Very High
10.	A pregnant woman can transmit HIV/AIDS to her unborn baby.	100	87.3	Very High
11.	HIV/AIDS cannot be transmitted by sharing food utensils of an infected person.	97	80.8	Very High
12.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by having a tooth extracted with the same devices after an infected person.	96	80	Very High
13.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by using an infected person's belongings such as clothes, comb, underwear, and towel.	96	80	Very High
14.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by having oral sex with an infected person.	93	77.5	High
15.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted with mosquito bites.	89	74.2	High
16.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by being exposed to an infected person who coughs and spits.	83	69.2	High
17.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by the urine of an infected person.	65	54.2	Moderately High
18.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by sharing a razor blade with an infected person.	62	51.7	Moderately High
19.	HIV/AIDS can be transmitted by having a tattoo.	47	39.2	Low

The researchers observed that a significant percentage of individuals (54.2%) believed that HIV/AIDS may be transferred through the urine of infected individuals, while 51.7% believed it can be transmitted through sharing a razor blade with infected individuals. Regrettably, a significant proportion (39.2%) obtained exceedingly poor results due to a misconception that HIV/AIDS can be transferred by tattooing. However, it is important to clarify that the transmission of the virus occurs when it leaves the body through various bodily fluids such as blood, breast milk, rectal fluid, semen, and vaginal fluid. HIV can persist in these bodily fluids outside of the body, but it requires prompt entry into another person's body for a new infection or co-infection to take place. During the discussion, it was found that a significant majority of the teachers shared the belief that AIDS can be transferred through vaginal intercourse with infected individuals. This belief was based on their understanding that sexual intercourse is the main source of HIV/AIDS.

It is a method of transmitting information. Only a small fraction of the teachers believed that HIV/AIDS can be transmitted through tattooing, as they were aware that tattoo needles are distinct from the needles used for drawing blood. They understood that tattoo needles are round, sealed, and incapable of retaining blood, unlike the needles used for administering vaccines. The study conducted by Murray et al. (2010) identified three primary modes of HIV transmission: sexual contact, considerable exposure to infected body fluids or tissues, and vertical transmission from mother to child during pregnancy, delivery, or breastfeeding. There is no possibility of contracting HIV if exposed to feces, nasal secretions, saliva, sputum, perspiration, tears, urine, or vomit unless these bodily fluids are contaminated with blood. HIV superinfection refers to the possibility of being co-infected by many strains of HIV. Sexual contact with an infected person is the primary means of transmitting HIV. The majority of global transmissions mostly occur through heterosexual contact, which refers to sexual contact between individuals of the opposite sex.

However, it is important to note that the specific pattern of transmission might vary greatly across different countries. As of 2010, the majority of HIV transmission in the United States was observed in men who engaged in sexual activity with other men. This specific group accounted for 65% of all newly reported cases (Boily Et al., 2009). HIV is spread through around 93% of blood transfusions using contaminated blood. In developed nations, the likelihood of contracting HIV through a blood transfusion is exceedingly low (less than one in every 500,000 cases) due to enhanced donor selection and HIV screening procedures. For instance, in the UK, the risk is estimated to be one in every five million cases, while in the United States it was one in every 1.5 million cases in 2008. As of 2008,

only 50% of transfusions in low-income countries undergo proper screening. It is believed that between 5% and 10% of global HIV infections are caused by transfusion of contaminated blood and blood products in these areas, accounting for up to 15% of infections.

Teachers' Awareness of HIV/AIDS in terms of Attitudes

Table 2C displayed the accurate response and percentage of HIV/AIDS awareness among teachers in relation to their attitudes. The researcher observed that a significant percentage of respondents expressed the following beliefs: individuals who are HIV positive and their families should seek counseling and join an HIV support group (92.5%); individuals with HIV should cease working and should not be permitted to continue their employment (90.8%); it is possible to work with people living with HIV/AIDS without contracting the virus (88.3%); and there is no necessity to take precautions when administering first aid (85%). The study found that a significant percentage of individuals living with HIV/AIDS (75%) have high scores in terms of their resemblance to the general population. Additionally, it was observed that HIV/AIDS individuals can still transmit the virus to others even if they test negative during the window period (65%). The study observed a 51% rate of individuals living with HIV/AIDS who are able to maintain good health and productivity despite their condition. In accordance with DepEd's (2012) curriculum, the present K-12 basic education curriculum tackles the issue by incorporating the examination of HIV/AIDS.

The Grade 8 MAPEH curriculum especially focuses on HIV/AIDS Education as part of its health component. This topic will be addressed during the first quarter of the academic year. It will specifically cover the many methods of HIV transmission and the preventive measures to avoid contracting the virus. The curriculum is designed to facilitate the development of students' decision-making abilities in the management of issues linked to sexuality. Teachers are responsible for providing age-appropriate teachings to assist pupils develop a comprehensive understanding of their sexuality and make informed decisions. Its primary objective is to reduce, if not eradicate, the social disapproval and prejudice against individuals affected by HIV/AIDS.

Table 2C. HIV/AIDS Awareness of Teachers in terms of Attitudes

Attitudes	Correct Responses	Percentage	Remarks
1. An HIV/AIDS-positive person and his/her family should see a counselor and an HIV support group.	111	92.5	Very High
2. If you are infected with HIV, you must stop working.	109	90.8	Very High
3. You should not allow HIV-positive people to continue working.	109	90.8	Very High
4. You can work with people living with HIV/AIDS and not get infected.	106	88.3	Very High
5. There is no need to take precautions when carrying out first aid.	103	85.8	Very High
6. A person with HIV/AIDS can infect others even though he/she tests negative during the window period.	79	65.8	High
7. People living with HIV/AIDS can remain healthy and productive.	62	51.7	Moderately High

The Philippine Government's response to the HIV danger was to pass the Philippine AIDS Prevention and Control Act of 1998 (Republic Act No. 8504). Congress passed this act following a lengthy process of careful consideration and support from the PNAC and other interested parties (Philippine National Aids Council (PNAC), 2004). The Act mandated a thorough and extensive HIV/AIDS educational and information campaign across the entire country. It also required the implementation of measures to ensure complete protection and the promotion of safe and universal precautions in practices and procedures that pose risks of HIV transmission. Additionally, the Act aimed to address the factors that worsen the spread of HIV infection and acknowledged the significant role that affected individuals could play in disseminating information and messages about HIV/AIDS. The legislation also mandates that local authorities must offer community-based services for the prevention, control, and care of HIV/AIDS.

Preventive Measures for HIV/AIDS Among Teachers Table 3 displayed the accurate answers and the corresponding percentage of teachers who implemented preventive measures against HIV/AIDS. The researcher observes that teachers obtained their information from various sources, including parents, schools, friends, newspapers, publications, the internet, and awareness initiatives, resulting in exceptionally high results (99%). During seminars, teachers acquire knowledge about HIV/AIDS from the speaker. They peruse periodicals and newspapers. When friends come over and exchange their expertise, they also utilize the internet for research. Approximately 96% of the teachers refrained from obtaining information through television and radio due to their preoccupation with school paperwork, seminars, and lesson planning.

The researcher observed in Table 3 that there were very high scores in relation to health education topics. Specifically, 97.5% of participants recognized the importance of checking the expiration date and condition of condoms before using them. Additionally, 92.5% of participants understood that it is unsafe to share needles and other injection equipment. Furthermore, 89.1% of participants acknowledged the significance of ensuring that all tubing and needles are free from contamination prior to a blood transfusion. Moreover, 85.5% of participants recognized that a woman can contract AIDS from her husband. Additionally, 84.2% of participants understood that condoms can prevent the transmission of AIDS. Lastly, 75.8% of participants correctly identified that HIV/AIDS cannot be transmitted through sweating. Nevertheless, the researcher observed a significant correlation between engaging in sexual activity with a familiar individual and the infection of AIDS, with a prevalence rate of 65%. Edewor (2010) asserts that information is crucial for human growth as it enhances the level of certainty in decision-making processes. In addition, Nwafor-Orizu (2009) explains

that various channels of communication are utilized in rural areas of Nigeria to disseminate information. These include oral sources such as direct conversations, radio, television, traditional institutions, associations, as well as written sources like newspapers and magazines.

Table 3. *HIV/AIDS Preventive Measures of Teachers*

<i>Preventive Measures of Teachers</i>		<i>Correct Responses</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Information				
1.	Parents	119	99.2	Very High
2.	School	119	99.2	Very High
3.	Friends	119	99.2	Very High
4.	Newspapers and Magazines	119	99.2	Very High
5.	Teachers	119	99.2	Very High
6.	Internet	119	99.2	Very High
7.	Awareness Program	119	99.2	Very High
8.	Television	116	96.7	Very High
Health Education				
1.	You must check the condom for expiry and condition before use.	117	97.5	Very High
2.	It is safe to share needles and other injection equipment.	111	92.5	Very High
3.	It is important to ensure that all tubing, needles contaminated before a blood transfusion.	107	89.1	Very High
4.	A woman cannot get aids from her husband.	103	85.5	Very High
5.	Condom prevents AIDS.	101	84.2	Very High
6.	HIV/AIDS cannot be transmitted through sweating.	91	75.8	Very High
7.	Sex with a person whom you know very well can also cause AIDS.	78	65	High

The objective of employing these channels is to promote the transfer of information in rural areas, with the aim of eradicating ignorance and superstition. The current information and education campaign to prevent the spread of the disease should be pursued with great intensity, but some effort must also be directed towards the care of individuals who are already affected. (Akanmu and Akinsete, 2009). The findings of this study were consistent with Akpabio et al., (2009) in identifying insufficient knowledge as a significant factor contributing to high-risk heterosexual behavior. In Nigeria, sexual intercourse remains the primary method of HIV transmission. Several studies have consistently emphasized that the increase in the disease among young individuals can be attributed to factors such as engaging in sexual activities with multiple partners, initiating sexual experiences at an early age, and not consistently using condoms. These indicate a favorable disposition towards the sexual well-being of young individuals. These findings indicate that fostering a favorable outlook on sexual health among young individuals or implementing HIV/AIDS prevention initiatives could lead to favorable behavior and decrease the likelihood of risk. When individuals lack the ability to assert their rights and advocate for safe sexual practices owing to cultural, physiological, and socio-economic constraints. Approximately 43% of women had acknowledged being coerced into engaging in sexual activity, while 155 women felt compelled to have sex with their partners (Dore, Ungchusak, and Martin, 2010).

The correlation between teachers' awareness of HIV/AIDS and their implementation of preventive measures. Table 4 demonstrates a correlation between the level of HIV/AIDS awareness among instructors and the spread of information about HIV/AIDS through various media channels such as TV, radio, internet, and newspapers. Health education, on the other hand, did not demonstrate any correlation with HIV/AIDS awareness. This finding suggests that teachers exhibit a higher level of knowledge regarding the causes and prevention of HIV/AIDS when they are exposed to information from mass media channels such as television and radio, as well as print media like newspapers and magazines. Additionally, information obtained from schools, friends, other teachers, and awareness programs also contributes to their awareness. Therefore, this has resulted in the determination that the transmission of knowledge is crucial in order to enhance individuals' understanding of HIV/AIDS.

Table 4. *Relationship Between HIV/AIDS Awareness and Preventive Measures of Teachers*

<i>Preventive Measures on HIV/AIDS</i>	<i>HIV/AIDS Awareness</i>		
	<i>Correlation Coefficient (r)</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Information	0.283	.043	Significant
Health Education	0.017	.017	Not Significant

The correlation analysis revealed a significant association between the level of HIV/AIDS awareness among instructors and the dissemination of information. The correlation coefficient of 0.283, with a p-value of .043, demonstrates this relationship. Given that the p-value is less than .05, the association can be considered statistically significant. Nevertheless, there was no discernible association between HIV/AIDS Awareness and health education, as indicated by a correlation coefficient of 0.017 and a p-value of .017. Given that the p-value is more than 0.05, we can conclude that the link is not statistically significant. The study conducted by Merico (2013)

provides evidence for the substantial impact of information on HIV/AIDS awareness. This study demonstrates that community-based information initiatives encompass education and counseling to enhance HIV awareness and encourage behaviors that reduce the risk of infection. These initiatives also involve promoting HIV testing and counseling, providing appropriate treatment to HIV-infected mothers to prevent mother-to-child transmission (MTCT), offering micronutrient supplementation to pregnant and lactating women, and implementing interventions to improve treatment adherence through home visits. HIV prevention methods that are effective prioritize human dignity, accountability, voluntary engagement, and empowerment by providing access to knowledge, resources, and support networks (Merico et al., 2013). An in-depth comprehension of prevalent values and belief systems is essential for identifying constructive values and behaviors that can enhance and better support HIV interventions. Therefore, there is a growing endorsement of community-based strategies for HIV prevention. Community-based interventions (CBIs) are founded upon collective principles and standards, belief systems, and societal customs, and enable culturally responsive dialogues around HIV and sexual and reproductive health. This resulted in enhanced and more sophisticated understanding of HIV/AIDS.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that teachers have high knowledge about HIV/AIDS regarding its meaning, nature, causes, transmission, and prevention. Most of the teachers become aware of HIV/AIDS due to information they get from TV, radio, newspapers, magazines, and health education programs. It is therefore recommended that there would be a comprehensive information dissemination campaign about HIV/AIDS, their causes, transmission, and prevention not only among teenage students because they are mostly at risk of being infected by this disease.

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